

HISTORICAL CONTEXT AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF ATRIUM BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we summarized the history of the formation of the type of planning atriums . The author highlighted the similarities and differences between the palazzo , gallery , arcade and atrium . We consider the typology and classification of atriums at the architectural design of modern buildings . Based on the reviews of the modern buildings atrium-type , the author puts forward a hypothesis for further development of this type of planning based on new architectural technologies.

Introduction. Every year, modern architects increasingly design atriums. This practice is primarily used by foreign architects, but recently, the idea has gained popularity among Russian architects. The reason for the low popularity of this architectural design is the underutilization of the potential and functionality of atrium spaces.

Relevance. References to the construction of atriums first appear in Ancient Greece. Over the centuries, like any material object, atriums have evolved, beginning to perform functions and tasks not previously inherent to them. Currently, atrium construction is becoming increasingly popular every year. This trend is rapidly progressing due to the implementation of aesthetic and material aspects. With proper engineering and architectural calculations, these spaces can help save money on energy and gas heating. The above arguments create a particularly attractive atrium layout. type in the design of modern high-rise buildings.

The purpose of this study is to systematize knowledge about the history of atrium development and identify potential development prospects for this type based on the latest architectural technologies. Research in the fields of architectural history, design, art, and cultural studies served as the theoretical basis for this work.

Scientific novelty. Our chosen topic allows us to gain a more detailed understanding of the typology and classification of atrium spaces in high-rise building design .

Before studying the design of modern atrium architecture, it is necessary to define the concept of "atrium" and become familiar with the historical analogues of this planning type.

The atrium, one of the oldest archetypes of architectural composition, is a courtyard around which spaces of varying function are grouped. Atriums can take on any configuration: rectangular, square, circular, etc. Rooms and halls adjoin the atrium on one or more sides, allowing for a convenient interconnection of spaces of diverse character and lending them a compositional presence.

The first precursors to modern atriums were built in Ancient Greece, between the 5th and 2nd centuries BC. Atria began to appear on the periphery of living spaces. They were open courtyards surrounded by columns. During this period, the atrium underwent little transformation. In the first buildings, the central space was occupied by a hearth; later, hearths were replaced by shallow rectangular pools, above which was a hole for rainwater drainage.

In ancient architecture, there were three types of atriums: Etruscan, four-columned, and Roman. These structures regulated the microclimate of the home and served as the ceremonial spaces of ancient houses. Later, Middle Eastern courtyards, ancient Roman forums, temples, and theaters were built, and these became the prototypes of modern atriums.

During the Roman Empire, four-walled atriums were the primary design. Based on their placement within the building's volumetric layout, these atriums are considered built-in, and based on their microclimate control, they are considered cooling.

Parallel to the development of atriums, palazzos developed. Their forms and layouts were similar, but there were significant differences.

In Italian architecture, a palazzo is a palace, townhouse, or private home. The classic palazzo was a three-story building, rarely two or four stories high, facing the street. Its compositional center was an inner courtyard surrounded by arched colonnades. The ground floor of the palazzo housed service quarters, the second floor ceremonial rooms, and the third floor residential quarters [1].

The appearance of the early palazzo was distinguished by its closed, monolithic overall volume, as well as its austere appearance, in contrast to the lightness of its structures and the openness of its atria. However, over the centuries, the palazzo's form also evolved. For example, the 19th-century creation of the architect Sir Charles Barry, the London gentleman's Reform Club building (1841), became the originator of the modern atrium's appearance. The composition of this atrium was based on the form and plan of the Roman Palazzo Farnese. However, the architect introduced an innovation by enclosing the inner courtyard with a glazed metal vault. Thus, from 1841, a new stage in the design of atrium spaces began. In terms of microclimate control, 19th-century atria were warming, while in terms of their placement within the spatial structure, they were attached.

Following the incredible success of the London structure, atriums became a popular feature in the exteriors of cities across Europe and the United States. The Industrial Revolution gave the world the knowledge of how to create enormous volumes from glass and metal. New types of public spaces emerged – industrial exhibitions, greenhouses, pavilions, covered with large-span glazed decks combined with filigree metal systems. Greenhouses were added to country houses to create bright spaces with an artificial climate. This planning solution was created in response to society's need for public spaces protected from the bustle of the street and inclement weather. In the mid-19th century, new types of spaces emerged – linear, atrium-like spaces covered by glass street structures – arcades, galleries, and passages [2].

These types of architectural forms were also the precursors of modern atriums. Passages, arcades, and galleries had horizontally developed spaces, while atriums "grew" vertically. Atria are integrated into the building structure, while passages could be

independent features within the architectural environment. Another distinction of modern atriums lies in their functional significance. Unlike atriums, these structures primarily served pedestrian and commercial purposes, while atriums, as public spaces, serve a much broader purpose. Their primary function is to protect interior spaces from adverse environmental influences, but to ensure maximum sunlight penetration and for as long as possible, translucent glass was used as the enclosure material.

Based on these three functional basic principles, a generally accepted understanding of the modern design of atriums used in high-rise buildings has emerged.

An atrium in a high-rise building is a large multi-level space that unites two or more floors, located in the structure of a high-rise building, developed in a vertical direction and separated from the external environment by an enclosing structure that allows natural light to pass through [3].

The most important event in the development of modern atriums was the creation of the English engineer and architect Terry Farrell and Rolf Lebens introduced the concept of "buffer thinking" in 1980. The idea was that an atrium, oriented toward the most favorable direction in terms of sunlight and prevailing winds, serves as a buffer zone between the exterior and interior spaces by containing a large amount of air.

Thanks to the development of the "buffer thinking" concept, the double-enclosure principle has begun to be implemented in atrium construction. This principle, in turn, is subdivided into microclimate control types: heating, cooling, and transformable.

A heated atrium is especially indispensable in countries with predominantly cold weather. Thanks to the free penetration of sunlight, the air temperature inside is approximately 3-5 degrees higher than the surrounding atmosphere. Using a heated atrium can significantly reduce heating costs in adjacent spaces.

A cooled atrium is appropriate in hot and humid climates. This space becomes a shading structure, and the atrium acts as a shading system and a reservoir of cooled air. In warm and humid climates, on the other hand, the atrium is designed to allow for cross-ventilation.

A transformable atrium is effective in protecting against summer overheating and is also used during the heating season. The main feature of this atrium is the shading system of the exterior glazing. The primary purpose is to allow sunlight in during the winter, when the sun's angle of elevation is low, and to block direct sunlight during the summer, when the sun is high.

By implementing the concept of "buffer thinking," atrium spaces perform a number of functions essential to human life and building operations: increasing natural light, improving air circulation, acting as a climatic buffer; increasing the thermal efficiency of buildings; and "solar" heating.

Based on their location within a high-rise building, atriums are classified as closed or open. A closed atrium is an atrium with overhead lighting, consisting of several interconnected volumes; an open atrium is an atrium illuminated on one or more sides of the building, connecting two or more high-rise volumes.

According to the type of formation, atriums can be classified as: single-walled; double-walled; three-walled; four-walled; linear; multiple single-level atriums; podium-type; connecting several high-rise buildings; internal vertical atrium with inclusion of horizontal volumes; system of vertical atriums located along the perimeter.

Atriums have varied in their spatial character throughout history. From 1966 to 1987, the "city square— piazza " —characteristic prevailed . This approach united several buildings, creating a "vertical vestibule" that formed the building's entrance, illuminated the above- and below-ground floors, and connected the vertical transportation transfer levels. Such atrium layouts are often used as "winter gardens."

Between 1987 and 2005, the character of atrium spaces took shape, resembling "vertical neighborhood communes," uniting groups of spaces on different floors of the building. Since 2005, atriums have been designed as "vertical cities," atriums serving as "light and air ducts."

The challenges addressed by atrium structures in high-rise buildings from the late 20th to early 21st centuries have collectively formed a unified system that improves the architecture of these buildings. This system is becoming the primary design criterion.

Conclusion. Originating in antiquity, the atrium building type remains relevant in modern architectural design. Thanks to the development of new technologies in architectural construction, atriums are increasingly gaining popularity today, as evidenced by numerous completed projects for retail, business, entertainment, and other types of buildings. The reason modern architects frequently turn to atrium design solutions in high-rise buildings is the combination of functional, aesthetic, and technological means in organizing the space. An integrated approach to designing an atrium as a single, interconnected structure allows for the maximum optimization of the internal environment both at the spatial compositional level and in addressing the rational functional challenges of a modern building.

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